
A study on Employee Engagement practices for Sustainable Development in Human Resource with Respect to Biddano Pvt. Ltd. Pune.

Dr. Sarika Anil Bhosale¹ & Ms. Sanjivani Padawal²

¹Associate Professor, Yashoda Technical Campus, Satara

²MBA II Yashoda Technical Campus, Satara

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Abstract:

Sustainable Development of organisation is depend upon the Hr practices that effectively undertaken by the organisation. Engaging employees in right way is one of the key factors for the Sustainable Development of organisation. Skilled Employees which are engaged in organisation always leads highest productivity. Present research is about to find out different engagement practices that undertaken by organisation. Research study was related to the identifying influencing parameters which increase employee satisfaction and engage them with organisation. If organisation focuses on fostering supportive environment and managing work life balance in organisation they will in position to develop positive Employee Engagement practices.

Keywords: Employee Engagement, Sustainable Development, Human Resource

Introduction:

Financial and material resources cannot increase efficiency on their own. Any organization's ability to succeed or fail will rely on how well its employees work together to achieve its set goals, which calls for loyalty and dedication from all employees. Despite having a large number of skilled individuals, the business may not consistently meet quality and productivity standards. The organization ought to examine the causes of the inconsistent performance. Employee disengagement may be one of the causes. The success of an organization is correlated with employee engagement. Staff satisfaction and pleasure are not synonymous with staff engagement. An employee's happiness at work may be attributed to the organization and its objectives. It describes the level of enthusiasm and dedication a worker feels toward his/her job.

Biddano Pvt Ltd is a technology-driven company based in Pune, India. The company specializes in healthcare logistics

and supply chain solutions, leveraging technology to streamline and optimize the distribution of pharmaceuticals and medical supplies. Biddano aims to enhance the efficiency and reliability of the healthcare supply chain, ensuring timely delivery and availability of critical medical products.

In order to help pharmacies, distributors, and manufacturers better manage their operations, the company focuses on developing a smooth and integrated platform. Biddano tackles a number of issues in the healthcare logistics industry by utilizing cutting-edge technologies like data analytics, computerized inventory management, and real-time tracking. In order to improve patient care and health outcomes, Biddano's goal is to close the gap between supply and demand in the healthcare sector. Due to its dedication to innovation and technology, the company is positioned to play a significant role in changing the Indian healthcare supply chain environment.

Business success depends on employee engagement, which is a tactic used by organizations to try to strengthen their bonds with their workforce. However, few firms are able to effectively define metrics or manage this leadership style, therefore research on employee engagement is necessary for the organization's success and profitability.

Literature Review:

(MYILSWAMY1, August 2014.)

Employee engagement is strongly linked to organizational success, with engaged employees contributing significantly to performance and growth. Engagement drives employees' willingness to give their best efforts, fostering commitment and enhancing overall productivity. Organizations with a highly engaged workforce experience better organizational effectiveness, improved performance, and greater work-life balance. Engagement is crucial for retaining talent, improving job satisfaction, and driving long-term success in a competitive market.

(Hammoud, 2017)

Rewards and recognition, where leaders acknowledge employee achievements to boost motivation; Empowering employees, through providing autonomy and responsibility, leading to higher job satisfaction; and Building strong relationships between leaders and employees, fostering trust and communication. These strategies were supported by the self-determination theory, emphasizing the importance of autonomy, competence, and relatedness in driving engagement.

(Kumar, July 2016)

The importance of employee engagement in enhancing organizational effectiveness. Engagement is a two-way process that boosts productivity, performance, and employee commitment to organizational goals. It positively impacts both non-financial outcomes, such as customer satisfaction and retention, and financial outcomes, like profitability. Engagement

also fosters team dynamics, cultural democracy, and a learning environment, leading to improved employee attitudes, behaviors, and overall performance. Organizations must prioritize employee engagement to maintain a competitive advantage.

(Motyka*, 2018)

Significant Link Between Engagement and Performance – Most studies confirm a statistically significant positive relationship between employee engagement and various performance categories. Impact on Multiple Performance Aspects – Engaged employees contribute to higher productivity, better customer satisfaction, and improved financial performance. Gaps in Research Identified – There is still a need for more studies on long-term engagement effects and industry-specific insights. Practical and Theoretical Implications – The findings provide valuable recommendations for both organizations and researchers to enhance engagement strategies.

(Saks, June 2006)

Job and organization engagement are distinct but related concepts. Perceived organizational support, job characteristics, and procedural justice predict engagement. Engagement mediates the relationship between its antecedents and outcomes like job satisfaction and commitment. The study provides empirical evidence that engagement is a crucial factor, not just a management fad.

(Pillai, 2019)

Employee engagement positively impacts employee performance. Key factors influencing engagement include pay, benefits, leadership, training, and career development. Employees are generally satisfied with the overall performance of the company. All identified engagement factors contribute positively to organizational performance.

(Carter, september 2018)

Both self-efficacy and employee engagement significantly impact individual

job performance. The study found that these factors together explained 12% of appointments made and 39% of products sold beyond past performance. There is a lack of rigorous individual-level studies on self-efficacy and engagement in business settings. HRM practitioners should focus on enhancing both self-efficacy and engagement to improve employee performance.

(Nikolova, 20 feb 2019)

Engaging leadership influences job resources like autonomy and colleague support but does not directly predict learning opportunities or work engagement over time. A reverse effect was found—employee engagement at T1 shaped perceptions of engaging leadership at T2. Engaged employees reported higher job resources over time, highlighting the dynamic relationship between engagement and workplace resources. A simple cause-effect model is insufficient; a more comprehensive approach is needed to understand how leadership and engagement interact. Organizations should focus on both leadership development and fostering an engaging work environment to sustain high employee engagement.

(Hammoud, Effective Employee Engagement in the Workplace, 2017)

Employee engagement is crucial for maintaining profitability and adapting to change in corporate industries. Disengaged employees negatively impact financial performance, while higher engagement boosts productivity and profitability. Balancing employee relations, innovation, and short-term profits is key to organizational sustainability. Interpersonal behaviors and engagement levels directly influence organizational productivity and long-term success.

Management Problem:

Biddano Pvt. Ltd., Pune, is facing critical human resource challenges, including an increasing Employee Turnover

Ratio (ETR), declining productivity, and a rise in work rejections. A major contributing factor to these issues is low employee engagement, leading to dissatisfaction among workers. Employees are leaving their jobs due to lack of job satisfaction, unclear vision and goals, limited career growth opportunities, and poor work-life balance, all of which indicate gaps in the company's engagement strategies.

Recognizing these challenges, the management seeks to assess the current status of employee engagement, identify key problem areas, and evaluate the impact of HR practices such as training and development, performance management, career progression, leadership effectiveness, work-life balance initiatives, and communication strategies. This study aims to analyze these factors to provide actionable insights for optimizing employee engagement, reducing turnover, enhancing productivity, and improving overall workforce stability for sustainable HR development.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To identify the various factors that influencing employee engagement.

Research Methodology:

The research conducted in Biddano Pvt. Ltd., Pune, State of Maharashtra, India. The scope of the study is limited Biddano Pvt. Ltd., Pune, only. The research study is descriptive in nature. It uses a Schedule as the research tool. The specific goal of this research is to identify the various factors that influencing employee engagement. For the study 106 samples are selected by convenient random method from the available finite population As to survive in cut troth competition employees engagement is the best tool for retaining employee in organisation for the sustainable growth of the organisation

Data Analysis:**Table No: 1: Opinions of Respondents for Mental health. (n=106)**

Sr.No.	Responses	Frequency	Percentage
1	Satisfied	17	16.04
2	Neutral	57	53.77
3	Dissatisfied	29	27.36
4	Very dissatisfied	3	2.83
	Total	106	100.00

(Source: Primary data Source)

Above table shows that maximum i.e. 53.77% respondents shows neutral opinion about mental health supports at workplace, 27.36% respondents are shows Dissatisfied opinion about at mental health supports at workplace, 16.04% respondents shows

Satisfied opinion about mental health supports at workplace, and remaining 2.83% respondents are shows that Very Dissatisfied mental health supports at workplace.

Table No : 2 : Opinions of Respondents for Job responsibility.

Sr.No.	Responses	Frequency	Percentage
1	Very clear	8	7.55
2	Somewhat clear	40	37.74
3	Neutral	43	40.57
4	Somewhat unclear	10	9.43
5	Very unclear	5	4.7
	Total	106	100

(Source: Primary data source)

Above table shows that maximum i.e. 40.57% respondents shows neutral opinion about statement like organization running in such a culture where job clarity is given to the worker that is Job responsibility.

37.74% respondents are says that clarity of employees job responsibilities are Somewhat clear, 9.43% respondents are says that clarity of employees job responsibilities are Somewhat unsatisfied, and remaining 7.55% respondents are says that clarity of employees job responsibilities are very clear.

Table No : 3 Opinion of Respondents for Growth opportunities. (n=106)

Sr.No.	Responses	Frequency	Percentage
1	Regularly	21	19.81
2	Occasionally	59	55.66
3	Rarely	23	21.70
4	Never	3	2.83
	Total	106	100.00

(Sources: Primary data sources)

Above table shows that maximum i.e. 55.66% respondents says that Occasionally they receive opportunities for growth and development, 21.70%

respondents are saying that Rarely they receive opportunities for growth and development, 19.81% respondents are saying that Regularly they receive

opportunities for growth and development, and remaining 2.83% respondents are saying

that they Never receive opportunities for growth and development.

Table No 4: Opinion about factors influencing employee engagement.

Sr	Particulars	Average	Std.Dev.
1.	My job provides growth opportunities and advancements.	4.04	0.85
2.	Our organization has a collaborative culture that promotes teamwork.	3.82	0.86
3.	My supervisor supports and empowers me in my decision.	3.60	1.04
4.	I have autonomy in my job	3.54	1.02
5.	Regular feedback and recognition improve my engagement.	3.59	0.90
6.	Our organization promotes open and transparent communication	3.59	0.93
7.	My work has purpose and meaning, fostering a sense of belonging.	3.45	0.97
8.	I am satisfied with the company's healthy insurance and retirement plan.	3.79	0.97
9.	I receive adequate paid time off (vacation, sick leave, etc.)	3.60	0.94
10.	The company offers wellness programs and employee assistance for personal issues.	3.58	0.94
11.	The company provides opportunities for professional development and training.	3.63	1.02
12.	My work schedule allows for adequate personal time and balance between work and family.	3.58	0.94
13.	The company respects my personal boundaries.	3.53	1.05
14.	The company's reward system is fair and motivating.	3.50	0.94
15.	Overall, I feel engaged valued, and satisfied with my job.	3.44	1.06

(Source: Primary data source)

Above table shows that agreement of among respondent on the various factors influencing employee engagement. The most influencing factor is, "My job provides growth opportunities and advancement" is rated 4.04 Mean score shows that samples are agreed with the job provides growth opportunities and advancement is the most influencing factor. Standard deviation is 0.85 shows consistency in opinions. Next factors influencing "Our organization has a collaborative culture that promotes teamwork." with 3.82 Mean score shows that samples are agreed with the Our organization has a collaborative culture that promote steam work. Standard Deviation is 0.86 shows consistency in opines. Next factor influencing is, "I am

satisfied with the company's health insurance and retirement plan". With 3.79 Mean score shows that samples are agreed to the I am satisfied with the company's health insurance and retirement plan. Standard Deviation is 0.97 shows consistency in opines. Least factor influencing, "Overall, I feel engaged valued, and satisfied with my job", with 3.44 Mean score shows that samples are agreed to the fact that overall, employees feel engaged valued, and satisfied with their job. Standard Deviation is 1.06 shows consistency in opinions.

Factor Analysis:**Factors Influencing Employee Engagement:**

Following is the analysis of parameters that shows influencing factors which considered to be most important in organization for

engaging employees in the right way. The table shows KMO and Bartlett's Test for Factors Influencing Employee Engagement. Factor analysis has used to find out factors out of these fifteen statements.

Table No 5: KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.912
	Approx. Chi-Square	1184.136
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	df	105
	Sig.	.000

(Source: Compiled by researcher)

The **Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) Measure of Sampling Adequacy** value is 0.912, indicating that the data is highly suitable for factor analysis. A KMO value above 0.9 reflects an excellent level of sampling adequacy.

The results of **Bartlett's Test of Sphericity** show a Chi-Square value of 1184.136 with 105 degrees of freedom, and the significance level is 0.000. This indicates that the correlation matrix is not an identity matrix and confirms the suitability of the data for factor analysis.

Table No 6

Communalities		
	Initial	Extraction
F1	1.000	.653
F2	1.000	.634
F3	1.000	.703
F4	1.000	.671
F5	1.000	.505
F6	1.000	.684
F7	1.000	.706
F8	1.000	.617
F9	1.000	.539
F10	1.000	.592
F11	1.000	.739
F12	1.000	.710
F13	1.000	.753
F14	1.000	.676
F15	1.000	.690
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.		

(Source: Compiled by researcher)

This table presents the communalities for each variable before and after extraction using Principal Component Analysis (PCA). The "Initial" values are set to 1.000, indicating that each variable initially possesses its total variance. The "Extraction" values represent the portion of variance retained in the extracted components. Higher values indicate that a greater proportion of variance is explained by the selected components, suggesting strong representation in the factor structure.

Notably, F13, F11, F12 exhibit the highest extracted communalities, indicating a substantial proportion of their variance is explained. Conversely, F5 and F9 have the lowest communalities, implying that a smaller proportion of their variance is captured by the extracted components

Table No 7: Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	8.723	58.153	58.153	8.723	58.153	58.153	5.466	36.443	36.443
2	1.150	7.666	65.819	1.150	7.666	65.819	4.406	29.376	65.819
3	.973	6.489	72.308						
4	.746	4.971	77.279						
5	.541	3.607	80.886						
6	.502	3.349	84.235						
7	.409	2.726	86.961						
8	.363	2.423	89.384						
9	.317	2.112	91.496						
10	.279	1.858	93.354						
11	.265	1.764	95.119						
12	.234	1.563	96.682						
13	.204	1.357	98.039						
14	.189	1.260	99.299						
15	.105	.701	100.000						

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

(Source: Compiled by researcher)

Above table shows that the data explains is 65.81% of variance with two factors. The rotated component matrix has been utilized to get final factor scores.

Table No 8: Rotated Component Matrix^a

Sr. No	Parameters	Component	
		1	2
1.	My job provides growth opportunities and advancements.	.744	.316
2.	Our organization has a collaborative culture that promotes teamwork.	.757	.245
3.	My supervisor supports and empowers me in my decision.	.774	.323
4.	I have autonomy in my job	.629	.525
5.	Regular feedback and recognition improve my engagement.	.651	.287
6.	Our organization promotes open and transparent communication	.761	.324
7.	My work has purpose and meaning, fostering a sense of belonging.	.771	.334
8.	I am satisfied with the company's healthy insurance and retirement plan.	.689	.377
9.	I receive adequate paid time off (vacation, sick leave, etc.)	.658	.325
10.	The company offers wellness programs and employee assistance for personal issues.	.486	.597
11.	The company provides opportunities for professional development and training.	.477	.715
12.	My work schedule allows for adequate personal time and balance between work and family.	.341	.771
13.	The company respects my personal boundaries.	.335	.801
14.	The company's reward system is fair and motivating.	.249	.783
15.	Overall, I feel engaged valued, and satisfied with my job.	.292	.778

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis. Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.

a. Rotation converged in 3 iterations.

(Source: Compiled by researcher)

Above Table shows the reasonable factor loading to every statement. The factors with respect to statements are labelled by researcher as follows.

Table No 9: Factor: Supportive Work Environment

Sr. No.	Factors	Factor Loading
1.	My job provides growth opportunities and advancements.	.744
2.	Our organization has a collaborative culture that promotes teamwork.	.757
3.	My supervisor supports and empowers me in my decision.	.774
4.	I have autonomy in my job	.629
5.	Regular feedback and recognition improve my engagement.	.651
6.	Our	.761
7.	My work has purpose and meaning, fostering a sense of belonging.	.771
8.	I am satisfied with the company's healthy insurance and retirement plan.	.689
9.	I receive adequate paid time off (vacation, sick leave, etc.)	.658

(Source: Compiled by researcher)

The Factor Supportive work environment highlights the parameters that influence employees be engaged in the organization. Theses factor has extracted owing to nine statements shows employee engagement practices undertaken in organization. The factor loadings suggest the relative importance of each parameter.

Table No 10: Factor: Work Life Balance:

Sr. No.	Parameters	Factor Loading
1	The company offers wellness programs and employee assistance for personal issues.	.597
2	The company provides opportunities for professional development and training.	.715
3	My work schedule allows for adequate personal time and balance between work and family.	.771
4	The company respects my	.801
5	The company' reward system is fair and motivating.	.783
6	Overall, I feel engaged valued, and satisfied with my job.	.778

(Source: Compiled by researcher)

Highest loaded factor, "My supervisor supports and empowers me in my decision." with 0.774 loading factor shows supervisors support leads the workers towards empowerment. Reaming statements which comes in this category suggest same employee engagement practices undertaken in organization.

The Factor Work Life Balance highlights the parameters that influence employees be engaged in the organization through balancing the work and life simultaneously. Theses factor has extracted owing to Six statements shows employee engagement practices undertaken in organization.

The factor loadings suggest the relative importance of each parameter. Highest loaded factor, "The company respects my personal boundaries." with 0.801 loading factor shows how oragisation can balance employees work and life simultaneously. Reaming statements which comes in this category suggest same employee engagement practices undertaken in organization.

Findings:

1. It is concluded that maximum i.e. 52.83% respondents are male in the research.
2. It is concluded that maximum i.e. 41.51% respondents are from age between 26 to

- 30 years and minimum i.e.2.83% respondents are from age between 40 and above years in the research.
3. It is concluded that maximum i.e.53.77% respondents shows neutral opinion about mental health supports at workplace.
 4. It is concluded that maximum i.e. 55.66% respondents says that occasionally receive opportunities for growth and development, and minimum i.e. 2.83% respondents are saying that Never receive opportunities for growth and development Never.
 5. Opinions about factors influencing employee engagement it is concluded that Most factors influencing is, “My job provides growth opportunities and advancements”. With 4.04 Mean score shows that samples are agreed with the fact that job provides growth opportunities and advancements. Standard deviation is 0.85 shows consistency in opines and Least factor influencing is “The company offers wellness programs and employee assistance for personal issues” with 3.58 Means cores hows that samples are agreed to the fact The company offers wellness programs and employee assistance for personal issues. Standard Deviation is 0.94 shows consistency in opines.
 6. The **Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) Measure of Sampling Adequacy** value is 0.912, indicating that the data is highly suitable for factor analysis. A KMO value above 0.9 reflects an excellent level of sampling adequacy.
 7. The Factor Supportive work environment highlights the parameters that influence employees be engaged in the organization. Theses factor has extracted owing to nine statements shows employee engagement practices undertaken in organization. The factor loadings suggest the relative importance of each parameter. Highest loaded factor, “My supervisor supports and empowers me in my decision.” with 0.774 loading factor shows supervisors support

leads the workers towards empowerment.

8. The Factor Work Life Balance highlights the parameters that influence employees be engaged in the organization through balancing the work and life simultaneously. Theses factor has extracted owing to five statements shows employee engagement practices undertaken in organization. The factor loadings suggest the relative importance of each parameter. Highest loaded factor, “The company respects my personal boundaries.” with 0.801 loading factor shows how oragisation can balance employees work and life simultaneously.

Suggestions:

- Company should implement regular feedback and recognition programs to boost employee morale.
- Company should introduce flexible work arrangements and wellness initiatives to enhance work-life balance.

Conclusion:

The comprehensive study on employee engagement in Bidaano Pvt Ltd, Pune, yielded valuable insights in to the complex dynamics influencing employee motivation and job satisfaction. The findings underscored the significance of effective communication, recognition, work-life balance, and growth opportunities in fostering a culture of engagement. Notably, inadequate feedback, limited career advancement prospects, and burnout emerged as key challenges undermining employee engagement. To address these issues, the study recommends implementing regular feedback mechanisms, recognition programs, flexible work arrangements, wellness initiatives, and employee development opportunities. By integrating these strategies, Bidaano Pvt Ltd can enhance employee engagement, retention, and productivity, ultimately driving business growth and establishing itself as a preferred

employer.

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